

This code was used to produce Fig. 4d

The details can be found in the Methods section of Mehl. et al. 2024

Fractional contribution calculation

Dye case

the phasor location is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbf{p} = \frac{[bound]\epsilon_b\mathbf{p}_b + [free]\epsilon_f\mathbf{p}_f}{[bound]\epsilon_b + [free]\epsilon_f} \quad (1)$$

ϵ_f and ϵ_b are the relative brightness of the free and bound states of the biosensor. With the knowledge of these phasor locations along with the relative brightness of the two states, the fraction of bound biosensor, F_b can be calculated.

$$F_b = \frac{\frac{[bound]}{[free]}}{1 + \frac{[bound]}{[free]}} = \frac{\frac{\epsilon_f \|\mathbf{p}_f - \mathbf{p}\|}{\epsilon_b \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_b\|}}{1 + \frac{\epsilon_f \|\mathbf{p}_f - \mathbf{p}\|}{\epsilon_b \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_b\|}} \quad (2)$$

next we define:

$$\alpha = \|\mathbf{p}_f - \mathbf{p}\|; \beta = \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_b\|; \mathbf{r} = \frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_b}.$$

with some rearrangement...

$$\frac{\alpha}{\beta} = \frac{F_b}{\mathbf{r}(1 - F_b)}$$

then the fractional contribution of the active form:

$$fractional_contribution = \frac{\beta}{\alpha + \beta} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{\beta}}$$

```
% dye case

% free to bound ratio
brightness_f2b = 1;
brightness_f2b2 = 0.1;

% scan activation level from 0 - 100 %
fraction_bound = linspace(0, 1, 100);

fraction_contribution = zeros(length(fraction_bound), 1);
fraction_contribution2 = fraction_contribution;

ii = 0;
```

```

for i_fraction_bound = fraction_bound
    ii = ii + 1;
    i_fraction_free = 1 - i_fraction_bound;

    alpha_divide_beta = i_fraction_bound / (brightness_f2b * (1 -
i_fraction_bound));
    alpha_divide_beta2 = i_fraction_bound / (brightness_f2b2 * (1 -
i_fraction_bound));

    fraction_contribution(ii) = alpha_divide_beta/(alpha_divide_beta + 1);
    fraction_contribution2(ii) = alpha_divide_beta2/(alpha_divide_beta2 +
1);
end

```

FRET (or quenching) case

Typically, the FRET efficiency is calculated as:

$E_{FRET} = 1 - \frac{\tau_{da}}{\tau_d}$, where τ_d is the single exponential lifetime of the unquenched donor and τ_{da} is the quenched lifetime of the donor.

Alternatively, $E_{FRET} = 1 - \frac{I_{da}}{I_d}$, where I_{da} and I_d are the relative brightness of the quenched and unquenched donor.

```

% analogy to acceptor-bleaching FRET (apFRET)
% E = 1 - I_DA/I_D
% also see doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2020.105401

```

In this case, $\frac{\epsilon_f}{\epsilon_b} = \frac{I_d}{I_{da}} = \frac{1}{1 - E_{FRET}}$. The following derivation is similar to above.

```

% FRET case
E1 = 0.5; % FRET when active
E2 = 0.5; % FRET when inactive

brightness_f2b = 1/(1 - E1);
brightness_f2b2 = 1 - E2;

fraction_bound = linspace(0, 1, 100);
fraction_contribution3 = zeros(length(fraction_bound), 1);
fraction_contribution4 = fraction_contribution;

ii = 0;

```

```

for i_fraction_bound = fraction_bound
    ii = ii + 1;
    i_fraction_free = 1 - i_fraction_bound;

    kk = (1 - i_fraction_bound)/i_fraction_bound;

    alpha_divide_beta = (brightness_f2b - i_fraction_bound *
brightness_f2b)/i_fraction_bound;
    alpha_divide_beta2 = (brightness_f2b2 - i_fraction_bound *
brightness_f2b2)/i_fraction_bound;

    fraction_contribution3(ii) = 1/(1 + alpha_divide_beta);
    fraction_contribution4(ii) = 1/(1 + alpha_divide_beta2);
end

```

```

figure;
title('Fractional contribution of the bound biosensor')
hold on;
% plot dye sensor
plot(fraction_bound, fraction_contribution, 'b-' , 'LineWidth', 2);
plot(fraction_bound, fraction_contribution2, 'b--' , 'LineWidth', 2);
% plot FRET sensor
% plot(fraction_bound, fraction_contribution3, 'r-' , 'LineWidth', 2);
% plot(fraction_bound, fraction_contribution4, 'r--' , 'LineWidth', 2);
hold off;

xlabel('Active protein (%)');
ylabel('Fractional Contribution');

axis equal;
axis([0, 1, 0, 1]);
xticks(0:0.2:1);
yticks(0:0.2:1);
grid on;
ax = gca;
ax.XAxis.FontSize = 16;
ax.YAxis.FontSize = 16;

% legend({'\epsilon_f/\epsilon_b = 1.0', '\epsilon_f/\epsilon_b = 0.1', 'E
= 50% FRET: active', 'E = 50% FRET: inactive'}, ...
%      'Location',"best");

legend({'\epsilon_f/\epsilon_b = 1.0', '\epsilon_f/\epsilon_b = 0.1'}, ...
      'Location',"best");

```

